

A NOTE ON THE TWO DIFFERENT MODIFICATIONS OF COBALT QUINALDINATE.

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Quinaldinic acid has been introduced by Rây and Bose (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1933, 95, 400) as a reagent for the estimation of Cu, Zn, Cd and U, and for their separation from various other elements and radicals. The authors have also described (*loc. cit.*) a number of metallic salts of the acid, and the occurrence of two different modifications of the ferrous quinaldinate (*cis*- and *trans*- form) has been accounted for. It has now been observed that the cobalt quinaldinate also exists in two different modifications—one cream-coloured and the other rose-red. Though they differ only in the water of hydration, the red variety being anhydrous, it was found interesting to study their mode of formation, conditions of mutual transformation and their characteristic properties.

Mode of Formation.

1. When a neutral solution of any cobalt salt is added to a neutral solution of sodium quinaldinate in the cold, a cream-coloured precipitate is formed ; on boiling, the precipitate becomes granular.

2. When the cobalt salt solution is acidified with a drop or two of acetic acid and then treated with sodium quinaldinate solution in the cold, the cream-coloured precipitate is formed as before ; but on keeping the mixture on the water-bath for some time, the precipitate changes into the rose-red crystalline variety.

3. When a slightly acidified (with acetic acid) hot cobalt salt solution is mixed with a hot solution of sodium quinaldinate, the rose-red precipitate is formed at once.

These facts show that the presence of H⁺ ion coupled with rise of temperature (80–90°) favours the formation of the red variety or the transformation of the cream-coloured product into the latter.

The cream-coloured variety was, however, found to be stable in the dry state even up to a temperature of 160°, above which it lost its water and changed into the red modification.

Magnetically both the substances were paramagnetic, the red variety giving a somewhat smaller susceptibility value.

TWO DIFFERENT MODIFICATIONS OF COBALT QUINALDINATE 573

Cobalt Quinaldinate (cream).—The cream-coloured variety was prepared in the cold as described under 2. The precipitate was washed with cold water and dried in *vacuo* over concentrated H_2SO_4 to a constant weight. [Found: N, 6'20; Co, 13'47, 13'50. Co $(C_{10}H_8NO_2)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ requires, N, 6'25; Co, 13'46 per cent].

Cobalt Quinaldinate (red).—The red anhydrous variety was obtained as described under 3. This was washed with hot water and dried as in the previous case. [Found: N, 6'90; Co, 14'60, 14'50. Co $(C_{10}H_8NO_2)_2$ requires N, 6'95; Co, 14'61 per cent].

Magnetic Susceptibility.

At 23°.	$\chi_m \times 10^6$.	$\chi_M \times 10^6$.	P_{weil}
Cream salt	... 20'19	8863'4	22'82
Red salt	... 19'21	7741'63	21'27

The measurements were made in a Curie's balance. P_{weil} for Co-atom either as free Co^{++} ion or in complex cobaltous salts (imperfect or associated complexes) has been found to vary between 22—26.

Both the cream and red cobalt quinaldinates are evidently co-ordination compounds of the imperfect or associated type. The co-ordination number for the central cobalt atom in the cream-coloured hydrated compound is six, whereas in the rose-red variety it is four only. It may be further assumed from a consideration of the colour of the salts that the two water molecules in the hydrated cream-coloured modification occupy *trans*-positions. These molecules of water cannot be removed below 160° and, therefore, form actually a part of the co-ordination complex.

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